

PREVALENCE OF CERVICAL CANCER AND PRECANCEROUS LESIONS IN WOMEN BY USING PAP SMEAR AND HPV PCR

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Abstract

Cervical cancer is the fourth most widespread cancer in women. Human papillomavirus (HPV) has been linked to about 80-90% of all cases of cervical cancer. This disease primarily has an effect on women belongs from low- and lower-middle-income countries, where 90% of cases happen, and Pakistan is one of them. This study aimed to evaluate the prevalence of HPV among adult women by analyzing results of Pap smear and HPV polymerase chain reaction (PCR) and to find the association of age group with precancerous lesions and cervical cancer. This was a retrospective descriptive cross-sectional study. Data was collected in February 2026 from Hameed Latif Hospital Laboratory. The sampling technique was consecutive sampling. A total of 108 female participants were included in the study. Data was analyzed using SPSS version 27, and Chi Square test was applied to find the association. Data was presented both in graph and tabulated form. The findings showed that the majority of the female participants were from the age group of 35-39 years. Cancer was reported among females aged 45-49 and 55-59. 22.2% of the females were detected with positive HPV (HR-HPV). 67.5% cases had abnormal Pap smear, with 50% cases of inflammation, 1.85% of ASCUS, 13.8% of mild to moderate abnormalities in cervical cells exhibiting precancerous lesions, while 1.85% cases were of severe abnormality, suggestive of invasive cancer. The majority of the female participants showed signs of low-grade intraepithelial lesion (8.3%), followed by HSIL (5.5%) and cervical cancer. It also reported a significant association between age groups and development of cancer ($p < 0.05$). The study reports that the prevalence of cervical cancer remains an important women's health concern. Overall, the study contributes to a better understanding of the pattern of cervical cancer and underscores the importance of continued research.

INTRODUCTION

Cervical cancer develops in the lower portion of the uterus called "cervix" that attaches to the vagina (Hamid et al., 2025). This cancer is a major factor in malignancy-related death rates among women worldwide, with a notable proportion of

this challenge observed in developing countries such as Pakistan (Halim et al., 2026). A total of 5008 women every year in Pakistan are diagnosed with cervical cancer and have a mortality rate of 3197 (Awais et al., 2026). Globally, approximately 630 million population

are diagnosed with Human papillomavirus (HPV) (Liang et al., 2024), and has been linked to about 80-90% of all cases of cervical cancer (Babi et al., 2024), followed closely by the development of cervical intraepithelial neoplasia (CIN) grade 1, 2 and 3 and then it converts into cancer (Osmani et al., 2025).

HPV is the most prevalent disease that can be transmitted sexually. There are other risk factors as well that can cause cervical cancer, such as age, oral contraceptive use, and tobacco smoking (Babi et al., 2024). The process of causing the cancer has a bipolar pattern, the first peak that appears at the beginning of a woman's physical life, and then occurs the climacteric and postmenopausal phases in the second peak (Ahmed et al., 2026). There are more than 200 different types of HPV (Osmani et al., 2025) such as high-risk HPV (HR-HPV) type 16, 18, 31, 33, 35, 39, 45, 51, 52, 56, 58 and 59 while the HPV type 6 and 11 are the low-risk types (LR-HPV). Around almost 70% of the cases of the cervical cancer are due to the type 16 and 18 (Babi et al., 2024).

This disease primarily has an effect on women from low- and lower-middle-income countries (LMICs), where 90% of cases occur (Hamid et al., 2025), which includes Bangladesh, India, Nepal, Pakistan, Bhutan, Sri Lanka, Maldives (Mesquita et al., 2024). In 2020, the World Health Organization (WHO) introduced a program aimed at eliminating cervical cancer. The program outlines three goals to be met by 2030; to achieve 90% coverage of the HPV vaccine among girls aged 15 years and younger, to ensure that 75% of women up to 45 years of age complete two HPV tests, and to provide adequate treatment to 90% of patients (Chidebe et al., 2025).

Pap smear is the primary screening method for precancerous lesions. Measurement of nuclear size is the most important characteristic to interpret epithelial cell abnormality. Epithelial cell abnormalities include squamous intraepithelial lesion (SIL) category, which includes precancerous lesions of low-grade SIL (LSIL) to high-grade SIL (HSIL) and invasive squamous cell carcinoma (cervical cancer) (Shamsi et al., 2024). Regular screening through Pap smear has substantially lowered the burden; however, in Pakistan, screening uptake remains

low at approximately 2% (Alrajjal et al., 2021). In 2020, HPV testing was introduced as a second-test after Pap smear for women aged 35 years and older. This testing includes methods such as polymerase chain reaction (PCR), which is able to identify the type of HPV infection (Babi et al., 2024).

In 2019, the Expanded Program on Immunization (EPI) launched its first vaccine (Noreen et al., 2024). But Pakistan is still not among those nations that have initiated vaccination programs at their national level (Halim et al., 2026). However, in September 2025, Pakistan took a significant step by initiating its first countrywide HPV vaccination campaign targeting about 13 million girls aged 9 to 14 years with the support of Gavi, UNICEF and WHO (Halim et al., 2026). Therefore, this study aimed to evaluate the HPV prevalence rate among adult women by analyzing the results of Pap smear and HPV PCR and its association with women's age.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study Design:

The study design was a retrospective descriptive cross-sectional study design.

Settings:

The data was collected from Hameed Latif Hospital Laboratory.

Study Duration:

The study took 4 months after the approval of synopsis.

Sample Size:

108 patients were included in the study. The sample size was calculated through Cochran's formula.

Sampling Technique:

The sampling technique was consecutive sampling.

Sample Selection:

Participants were selected according to the following criteria.

- **Inclusion Criteria:**
 - Only females of age above 18 years were included.

- Both unmarried and married female participants were considered.
- Female participants screened for precancerous lesions and cervical cancer.
- **Exclusion Criteria:**
- Girls of age less than 18 years were not selected.
- Male of any age was not considered.
- Female participants with any other cancer including ovarian, vaginal etc.

Equipment/Technique:

The techniques used were the Pap smear and HPV PCR

Data Analysis

Data was presented in tabulated form and recorded in Microsoft Excel and analyzed using Statistical software (SPSS) version 27. Frequency and Percentage of the data were evaluated through Descriptive Statistics Analysis. Chi Square test was applied to find the association of age groups with precancerous lesions and cervical cancer. Statistics were considered significant for p-values less than 0.05. A low p-value indicated strong association between HPV infection and different age groups.

Ethical approval

The study was approved by the Research and Ethics Committee of Superior University, Lahore. All patient information was anonymized, and the data were used solely for the purpose of this research.

RESULTS

The results presented the frequency and percentage of marital status, age and screening methods, prevalence of abnormal Pap smear, precancerous lesions, positive cases of malignancy and detected HPV PCR in females. The results also presented an association between the development of cervical cancer and age groups.

Distribution Results of Characteristics of Participants

The demographic representation in table-1 showed that 1.9% of the women were single, 90.7% were married, while the status of 7.4% women was not known. Majority of women were from the age group of 35-34 years. 4.6% were from 18-24, 12% from 25-29, 9.3% from 30-34, 31.5% from 35-39, 20.4% from 40-44, 6.5% from 45-49, 69.3% from 50-54, 2.8% from 55-59, and 3.7% were from the age group 60 years or more.

Table-1: Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Marital Status		
Single	2	1.9
Married	98	90.7
Unknown	8	7.4
Age (years)		
18-24	5	4.6
25-29	13	12
30-34	10	9.3
35-39	34	31.5
40-44	22	20.4
45-49	7	6.5
50-54	10	9.3
55-59	3	2.8
>60	4	3.7

Distribution Results of Screening Methods of Participants

The findings of the present study showed that 96 females (88.8%) got screened using Pap smear,

103 females (95.3%) had HPV PCR, while 91 of the females (84.2%) were screened using both Pap smear and HPV PCR (Figure-1).

Figure-1: Distribution of Screening Methods

The results further showed that from the total sample of 108-participants, 67.5% (73) had abnormal Pap smear, while 22.2% (24) participants were detected with HPV positive (Figure-2)

Figure-2: Distribution of Abnormal Pap smear and Detected HPV

Distribution Results of Screening Methods of Participants

In general, the findings of Pap smear of 108-participants showed 21.3% normal cases, 67.5% cases were found with abnormality in their epithelial cells, while 11.1% participants don't have their Pap smear done. Among participants

with abnormal Pap smear, 50% cases showed inflammation, 1.85% cases had ASCUS, 13.8% showed mild to moderate abnormalities in their cervical cells exhibiting precancerous lesions (with 8.3% LSIL and 5.5% HSIL), while 1.85% cases had severe abnormality, suggestive of invasive cancer (Table-2).

Table-2: Frequency and Percentage of the Results of Pap smear (n=108)

Interpretation	Pap smear (n%)	Subtype	n%
Normal	23 (21.3%)	--	--
Abnormal	73 (67.5%)	Inflammatory	54 (50%)
		ASCUS	2 (1.85%)
		Precancerous Lesions	15 (13.8%)
		LSIL	9 (8.3%)
		HSIL	6 (5.5%)
Malignancy	2 (1.85%)		
Not Available	12 (11.1%)	--	--

While, among abnormal cases (73) of Pap smear, 73.9% cases showed inflammatory results, 2.7% had ASCUS, 20.5% showed mild to moderate

abnormalities in their cervical cells exhibiting precancerous lesions with 12.3% cases of LSIL and 8.2% cases of HSIL and 2.7% cases had

severe abnormality, suggestive of invasive cancer (Table-3).

Table-3: Frequency and Percentage of the Results of Abnormal Pap smear (n=73)

Interpretation	Pap smear (n%)	Subtype	n%
Abnormal	73 (67.5%)	Inflammatory	54 (73.9%)
		ASCUS	2 (2.7%)
		Precancerous Lesions	15 (20.5%)
		LSIL	9 (12.3%)
		HSIL	6 (8.2%)
		Malignancy	2 (2.7%)

Moreover, the prevalence of HPV infection observed in this study was 22.2%, with 24 cases found with detected HPV through HPV PCR. Results of the 24-participants with positive PCR showed that 8.3% cases were in single females and 91.7% were in married. 4.2% detected cases

were found with normal Pap smear with no signs of inflammation or cancer, 16.6% participants showed inflammatory results, 62.5% had mild to moderate abnormalities in their cervical cells, exhibiting (37.5%) LSIL and (25%) HSIL, 8.3% had cervical cancer (Table-4).

Table-4: Frequency and Percentage of the Results of Detected Cases of HPV and their Pap smear (n=24)

Interpretation	HPV PCR (n%)	Pap smear Results	n%
Detected HPV PCR	24 (22.2%)	Normal	1 (4.2%)
		Inflammation	4 (16.6%)
		Malignancy	2 (8.3%)
		Precancerous Lesions	15 (62.5%)
		LSIL	9 (37.5%)
		HSIL	6 (25%)
		Not Available	2 (8.3%)

Cancer Status Among Participants Based on Pap smear and HPV

Among total participants (n=108), 75% showed normal results (negative for malignancy but some had mild inflammation), 1.9% showed

severe abnormality in cervical cells indicating the presence of cervical cancer, 13.9% showed precancerous lesions (LSIL & HSIL), and 9.3% were the other cases (Figure-3).

Figure 3: Distribution of Cancer Status

While the other (10) cases had 3.7% of positive HPV cases, their Pap smear showed mild

inflammation (no signs of precancerous lesions). 1.9% had ASCUS, and their HPV PCR was

found negative, 1.9% cases showed positive HPV PCR, but their Pap smear was not available, therefore, the degree of abnormality in the cervical cells couldn't be found. 0.9% had an inflammatory Pap smear (no signs of cancer) but were not screened for HPV PCR, while 0.9 female was detected with HPV but had a normal Pap smear (no inflammation/cancer signs).

Cancer Status Among Participants Based on Age Groups

The findings also presented the distribution of cancer status based on different age groups. The two cases of cervical cancer were observed in the females from age groups 45-49 and 55-59. While majority of the precancerous cases were observed in females of 18-24 years, followed by 30-34 years (Figure-4).

Figure 4: Distribution of Cancer/Precancerous Lesions Based on Age Groups

In addition, Chi Square test was applied to find the association between HPV infection and different age groups. The findings showed a

significant association between age groups and the development of cancer or precancerous lesions (Table-5).

Table-5: Association Between Age Groups and Cancer/Precancer Lesion

Study Variable	Value	df	Significance Value
Pap Smear	50.291 ^a	40	0.128
HPV PCR	26.651 ^a	16	0.046
Age Groups	72.567 ^a	48	0.013

DISCUSSION

The results showed the highest prevalence of cervical cancer among females from age groups 45-49 and 55-59, while most cases of precancerous lesions were observed in the females of 18-24 years, followed by 30-34 years. A similar age group was reported in the previous study, where the general prevalence of positive cases was highest in women aged 50 to 60 years, followed by 40 to 50 years (Aziz et al., 2025). The prevalence of HPV infection observed in this study was 22.2% and was consistent with the previous research, where 16.7% of the participants were diagnosed with HPV infection (Jilani et al., 2025).

The study reported results of 108-participants with 50% inflammatory cases, 13.8%

participants showed mild to moderate abnormalities in their cervical cells exhibiting precancerous lesions with 8.3% cases of LSIL and 5.5% cases of HSIL, while only 1.85% cases had severe abnormalities, suggestive of invasive cancer. Inflammation was most observed in the women of age 35-39 years, followed by 40-44 years and based on the positive HPV PCR (24 cases) and 37.5% of females showed LSIL and 25% showed HSIL, while 8.3% had severe abnormality, suggestive of cervical cancer. These results were found to be consistent with the previous research. The findings showed that overall, 6% of the participants showed mild cervical cell abnormalities, indicating LSIL, while 1% had HSIL. Inflammation was most observed in the females aged 21 to 30 years, and

63.3% of the participants showed LSIL, while 60% cases were of HSIL, and no case of cervical cancer was found (Pirzada et al., 2022).

The present study found 67.5% (73/108) cases with abnormal Pap smear, with 12.9% (14) females showing dense inflammation, 13.8% (15) cases were of precancerous lesions (including LSIL and HSIL), while 1.85% (2) females showed positive results for malignancy. Similar research was conducted by Qayyum et al, from September 2021 to April 2022, in MTI-Khyber Teaching Hospital to evaluate the number of abnormalities in 287 patients. As per the findings, 20.6% patients had dense inflammation, 22.3% samples were negative for malignancy, while 7.0% samples showed epithelial cell abnormality, including CIN exhibiting precancerous lesions (Qayyum et al., 2024).

The majority of the female participants (n=108) showed mild abnormalities in cervical cells, indicating LSIL (8.3%), followed by HSIL (5.5%) and cervical cancer (1.85%). These results were consistent with the previous report where LSIL has been observed the most as compared to others, thus showing a high prevalence rate of cytological changes in women performed by Naz et al., at DHQ Civil Hospital, Faisalabad (Naz et al., 2020). In addition, this study also showed a significant association between age groups and the development of precancerous lesions and cancer, with $p < 0.013$.

CONCLUSION

The study reports that the prevalence of cervical cancer remains an important women's health concern. Although cervical cancer is comparatively rare, its impact is significantly high as it is often detected late. The findings of this study present a significant association between the prevalence of cervical and women's age. This age-specific association emphasizes the importance of the development of standardized protocols and guidelines to ensure the consistency, quality and reliability of screening centers and vaccination programs. Overall, the study contributes to a better understanding of the population-based pattern of cervical cancer and underscores the importance of continued research aimed at increasing the screening rate and disease prevention.

Author Contribution

We declare that this work was conducted by the authors listed in this article, and all responsibilities related to claims concerning the content of this article are borne by the authors. Ayesha Zubair conceived and designed the study, contributed in drafting the manuscript, collected the data and interpreted the results. Fahad Shabbir contributed in formatting the manuscript. Khizra Zubair performed the data analysis and formatted and revised the manuscript. Zainab Zaka Khan edited and approved the final manuscript. Dr. Tahira Batool supervised the project and served as the corresponding author.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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